

Responsible Use of Student Data in AI - driven Educational System

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Abstract - This research paper discusses the dilemmas that come with the usage of Artificial Intelligence in Educational systems. The rapid adoption of AI technologies in this sector raises concerns for students, teachers as well as the organizations.[2][5] There are several ethical challenges related to the use of AI like the vast amount of student data that is continuously collected and analyzed for purposes like automatic grading, personalized learning etc.[2][4] which raises serious concerns in fields like education due to problems like transparency, biasness, inequality, data privacy etc which should be tackled as soon as possible to curb the long term disadvantages.[3][5] After doing a literature study, this paper tries to find the gaps in the current scenarios related to privacy, transparency, biasness and reliability issues of using AI and fill them by giving solutions which ensure optimal usage of AI in the educational sector.

Index Terms - AI, Education, Transparency, Explainability, Privacy Fatigue, Black Box, Student Data, Biasness.

INTRODUCTION

AI in the educational sector is wide-spreading in today's time. It has a lot of advantages like personalized, innovative and faster learning but also disadvantages like student data privacy, trustability and explainability.[4][3]

Due to the rise of digital learning platforms in the last 5 years, tools like AI are being used at a significant rate by students as well as teachers for tasks like automatic grading, content generation, doubt clearing, personalized content etc.[1][5] These tools most of the time rely on the vast amount of continuous student data for personalization which gives rise to serious concerns regarding the privacy of the data.[2][6]

As most of the time these data are stored on cloud for remotely and easily accessing the data rather than locally on device, it makes them vulnerable to cyberthreats like

hacking which can cause breaches of the private student data.[2][4]

Many AI models nowadays are too advanced to be interpreted by normal humans which becomes a trustability issue for students as to how the output is given, this type of technology is commonly known as 'Black Box' technologies.[3]

Many students don't care about their data when focusing on the features of AI and its numerous advantages. This data can be compromised if subjected to third party sites, hacking etc. Therefore, becoming a huge privacy concern. This phenomenon of getting attracted to the advantages while not caring about the privacy issues is known as 'Privacy Fatigue'.[1][6] This paper mainly focuses on these types of gaps in the educational sector.

This study surveys 6 different papers based on the above topic, finds gaps in the papers and tries to answer them.

LITERATURE SURVEY

I have selected 6 different research papers for this literature survey. The research papers were selected by multiple keyword combination subsets from AI, Education, Student Data Privacy, AI Transparency and AI Explainability. Multiple research papers were found using the keyword based search on IEEE Xplore and Google Scholar but the ones most related to the above topic were the 6 selected.

The main gaps from the papers include:

1. Student data privacy - The personalization part of AI educational models require a continuous stream of personal student data.[2][4] This vast collection of student data can become subject to privacy risks if shared with any third party sites or become subject to hacking.[4] Most of the time the data which is stored on the cloud by the organization is not secured / encrypted making

them vulnerable.[2] Sharing of this data to third party websites can also lead to misuse of the private data of the student like phishing attacks.[4]

2. Trustability and explainability - Students often become subject to a theorem known as 'Privacy Fatigue' where the student focuses more on the benefits of AI which overshadows the privacy risks.[1] In addition to that it is found that students have greater level of trust in the AI model if the backend processes of how the O/P is generated can be explained.[3][5] Most of the AI models are too hard to interpret by a normal human like neural networks which will work really well with good training data, and are very hard to interpret due to the number of hidden layers and computations. This is called a 'Black Box' model where we just give the input and get the output without completely understanding the underlying processing of how conversion from input to the output happened.[3]
3. Excessive usage - The widespread usage of AI by students helps them to provide more creativity in their work but most of the time makes them just blindly rely on them. This intercepts their learning process and can be harmful in the long term.[1][5] Students mostly depend on it for completing their stuff like assignments instead of using it as a helper which in a long term, hinders their learning process.
4. Biasness and inequality - As in supervised learning algorithms like regression, classification, decision trees, etc, all depend on the quality of training data. Hence, if the training data is more inclined about a particular group of people based on gender, race etc, it can lead to biases and inequality in the level of education per person.[4][5]
5. Lack of Accountability - Whenever a model makes an incorrect decision, there is a dilemma as to who is to be blamed for it, the developer, the organization or the dataset provider. This lack of accountability hinders the process of correcting errors.[3][5]

METHODOLOGY

This research paper tries to fill the gaps found in the literature survey by the following points:

I. Regulatory frameworks for AI ethics

Many big organizations have released their regulatory frameworks for AI ethics like UNESCO and EU GDPR which can be used in our case of protecting student data rights.

II. Privacy preserving techniques:

Usage of techniques like federated learning and differential privacy which allows in training and analyzing of the student data without exposing their raw personal information. This helps in protecting the student data while also training the AI model. Federated learning allows the model to be trained on the student's data locally on the student's device instead of sending the raw data to the cloud. On the other hand, differential privacy adds noise into the datasets of the students which protects the private information of the students. Also techniques like encryption on the cloud storage can significantly minimize privacy risks.

III. Transparency and Literacy:

Making AI models 'explainable'(i.e. - making models interpretable easily by humans) as it helps in increasing trust in the models O/P. This can be done by using visualization tools which diagrammatically explain each step in a simple AI model (like every decision made while traversing a decision tree to get an output). Also digital literacy programs can help in increasing understanding about how the data is being used by AI and how to control one's data.

IV. Removal of Biasness from a Model:

Biases of a model can be eradicated if the dataset the model is trained on is diverse and captures each fragment of the universal dataset for an unbiased output.

RESULT ANALYSIS

The AI model's complexity will only increase day by day as innovations grow in the technological field so it is very hard to fully interpret how one model works. But the trust in AI can be increased among people by importing the above points in the AI educational systems which will help in secure and reliable access of AI by students leading to more productive and faster results. As AI models heavily rely on the data, putting restrictions on it can significantly decrease the performance of the model. This trade off is one of the main challenges one has to think about before implementing a solution as to find the balance between them.

CONCLUSION

Through this research paper, the gaps found in literature review were addressed and tried to be filled using the points in methodology. This can help in increasing productivity among students by including AI in this field as a tool students trust and use to enhance their work as opposed to blindly relying on it or not trusting it. AI models, if used properly, can be a great helper in the field of education for the students. But there are many ethical challenges too which may overshadow the advantages. This paper provides solutions for the disadvantages for the optimal usage of AI.

REFERENCES

- [1] Tandiah, K., & Kurniawan, Y. (2025, August). Trust and Performance Outweigh Privacy: Generative Artificial Intelligence Adoption Among Undergraduate Students. In 2025 International Conference on Information Management and Technology (ICIMTech) (pp. 414-419). IEEE.
- [2] Huang, L. (2023). Ethics of artificial intelligence in education: Student privacy and data protection. *Science insights education frontiers*, 16(2), 2577-2587.
- [3] Contreras, M. R., & Jaimes, J. O. P. (2024, October). AI ethics in the fields of education and research: A systematic literature review. In 2024 International Symposium on

Accreditation of Engineering and Computing Education (ICACIT) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.

[4] Khan, W. N. (2024). Ethical challenges of AI in education: Balancing innovation with data privacy. *AI EDIFY Journal*, 1(1), 1-13.

[5] Ismail, M., Madathil, N. T., Alalawi, M., Alalawi, S., & Alrabaa, S. (2025, April). Navigating Ethical Dilemmas in the Implementation of AI-Driven Educational Technologies. In 2025 IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference (EDUCON) (pp. 1-5). IEEE.

[6] Jia, L., Lu, Y., Wang, Z., & Liu, J. (2025, September). The Impact of Privacy Sensitivity on AI Recommendation Adoption Among College Students. In 2025 International Conference on Culture-Oriented Science & Technology (CoST) (pp. 1-6). IEEE.

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